

NFDI4Earth

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Synthesis of NFDI4Earth Pilot Experiences

Living document synthesizing the roadmap from pilot experiences and community feedback

Veronika Grupp (veronika.grupp@uni-leipzig.de)

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Executive summary

NFDI4Earth pilot funding supports earth system science (ESS) researchers to tackle research data management (RDM) challenges in their subdomains. They have various aims from FAIR data provision to enhanced software interoperability. We have synthesized their experiences based on their project reports in a simplified qualitative content analysis.

Pilot results have reached different levels of maturity by the completion of the one-year project phase. They have produced tools from prototypes to ready-to-use solutions and triggered discussions and processes on standards and RDM practices in their domains. As expected by NFDI4Earth pilot projects, the majority of the projects has shown to be committed to FAIR and open software, data and platforms and developed their solutions accordingly.

Depending on the subdomain the pilots faced specific challenges, being of rather technological nature (software integration) or more based on the structure, connectedness and habits of the sub-community. The pilot projects provide valuable insights into the diverse ESS sub-domains which support the overall strategy of NFDI4Earth to combine technological progress with community work.

Note: The document was updated with the latest inputs from pilots during the deliverable review phase and contains content from after the original deadline.

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1 Introduction

NFDI4Earth pilot projects were a major building block of the successful NFDI4Earth proposal in the second round of NFDI consortia. They were designed as an agile measure to engage with the ESS community, to financially support the solving of specific research data management (RDM) challenges in ESS subdomains and to use the pilot outcomes for requirements engineering in NFDI4Earth.

The first round of NFDI4Earth pilots were selected in the proposal phase and 10 of the 14 projects were finished in March 2023 after a one-year duration. The remaining four pilots will finish as scheduled in Q3/Q4 of 2023. Some pilots experienced delays in project initiation due to issues in the hiring process, while others were originally scheduled for durations exceeding 12 months. A second round of pilots will be selected by the end of May 2023 and start in August/September 2023. This synthesis report is designed as a living document and experiences of pilots will be added continuously after individual project completion. As of July 2023, ten pilot roadmaps are included in the present analysis (see section 3).

This synthesis report will combine the different experiences and outcomes of pilot projects described in the final roadmap document, delivered by each pilot at the end of the project duration¹. The roadmaps are comprehensive reports summarising the pilots' outcomes, challenges, gaps, and future directions, as well as the usage potential of their solutions. Based on different categories, we will discuss common challenges and obstacles in the projects' different endeavors to facilitate research data management workflows and show best practices and adoptions of the FAIR principles.

Within this report we will not give an exhaustive overview of the developed solutions and tools of individual pilots. For technical details and more elaborated information on the projects please refer to their roadmap documents referenced in section 3.

2 Methodology

To combine pilot outcomes and experiences into a synthesis all pilot roadmaps are thoroughly scanned and relevant passages and aspects regarding different categories are extracted and compiled. Based on this material, commonalities and differences are analyzed per category. The procedure can be compared to a qualitative content analysis, however minding the scope

¹ When referring to this document produced by each pilot at the end of the one-year duration, we will use the terms roadmap, roadmap document and roadmap report interchangeably. The term roadmap instead of project report was chosen in the initial proposal to highlight the nature of pilot projects to develop sustainable, promising solutions in RDM instead of answering a self-contained specific research question. The roadmap includes future directions and developments of the pilot solution, thus has a more forward-looking notion than a mere report on work accomplished.

and the non-scientific nature of this report the procedure is not as elaborated as in a scientific research process. Interpretation, recommendations, and selection of relevant aspects are derived based on the authors personal experience and expertise.

The author of this report (Veronika Grupp) acts as project coordinator and has accompanied the pilot projects with regular meetings and exchanges during the project phase. Thus, additional to content of the pilot roadmap documents, the present analysis is supplemented and influenced by personal impressions and conversations with the pilot researchers throughout the project phase. Section 5 contains lessons learned by the pilot coordination during the first pilot cohort, which are assembled by the authors experience and exchange with project colleagues and pilot projects.

As for the living nature of this document, the outcomes of each following pilot project will be analyzed as described above and text passages will be added in the results and conclusions sections upon their project completion.

For the further use and interpretation of the presented results please keep in mind, that NFDI4Earth pilot projects were specifically selected to represent different subdomains of ESS and to target different types of data. Consequently this is not a representative selection of ongoing processes or trends in ESS in Germany and doesn't necessarily reflect e.g., the size of a certain community (as of discipline or methodologically) and the importance of certain issues within the ESS.

3 Short overview of pilot projects

Here we provide a short summary of each completed pilot project with their names and the DOI of their roadmap report on Zenodo. In the following when referencing contents of a roadmap document we will only use the project name instead of a full citation for better readability.

Pilot Name	Short Summary
Complex Semantics	<p>Long title: Reusability of data with complex semantic structure</p> <p>Domain: Paleontology, paleoceanography, paleoclimatology</p> <p>Data: occurrence and abundance data of planktonic foraminifera from drill cores, long tail data</p> <p>Outcomes: R workflow to resolve semantics of inconsistent taxonomic identification of legacy data; community guidelines for new data publication standards.</p> <p>Roadmap: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8124211</p>
ESMValTool	<p>Long title: Enhancing Earth system model evaluation with data cube enabled machine learning</p> <p>Domain: Climate and earth system modelling</p> <p>Data: multivariate climate and earth system data, large, gridded data, data cubes</p> <p>Outcomes: Enhancement of existing model evaluation tool (ESMValTool) to handle data cubes in zarr format as input, software integration of an ML causal discovery algorithm.</p> <p>https://esmvaltool.org/</p> <p>Roadmap: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7826038</p>
GeoFRESH	<p>Long title: Getting freshwater spatiotemporal data on track – towards the interoperability of freshwater-specific data</p> <p>Domain: Freshwater research</p> <p>Data: river networks and and earth system data, vector data, large, gridded data</p> <p>Outcomes: Online platform where users can upload point data (e.g., biodiversity) and use various GIS functionalities for analysis and download of corresponding data accounting for the connected network structures and catchment areas.</p> <p>http://geofresh.org</p> <p>Roadmap: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7888389</p>

Pilot Name	Short Summary
Interop and Reuse	<p>Long title: Interoperability and Reuseability of Geoscientific Laboratory Data</p> <p>Domain: Geophysics, Petrophysics</p> <p>Data: raw and analysed data from geophysical laboratory measurements, i.e. petrophysical parameters of samples, long tail data</p> <p>Outcomes: Concept for a relational database model for metadata of a geoscientific laboratory work flow (from instruments to data evaluation)</p> <p>Roadmap: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8063264</p>
Lexcube	<p>Long title: Interactive Visualization and Exploration of High-Resolution Remote Sensing and Socioeconomic Data Sets</p> <p>Domain: Visualization, Computer Science</p> <p>Data: multivariate climate and earth system data, large, gridded data, data cubes</p> <p>Outcomes: Interactive online visualization tool to explore spatiotemporal patterns of various earth system datasets. https://www.lexcube.org/</p> <p>Roadmap: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7822389</p>
Marine Seismic Data	<p>Long title: German Marine Seismic Data Access</p> <p>Domain: Marine Geophysics</p> <p>Data: 2D and 3D large, gridded data</p> <p>Outcomes: overview and strategy of/for legacy data in Germany; development of a new standard for future data acquisition and archival. </p> <p>Roadmap: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7875451</p>
PAMbase	<p>Long title: Towards standardized soundscape recordings and analyses in Earth System Sciences</p> <p>Domain: Landscape Ecology</p> <p>Data: sound recordings</p> <p>Outcomes: Online platform to upload and analyze recordings from passive acoustic monitoring, integrated annotation tool, exploration of ML techniques for sound recognition. https://ecosound-web.de/ecosound_web/</p> <p>Roadmap: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7785327</p>

Pilot Name	Short Summary
Seamless Integration	<p>Long title: NFDI for seamless Earth system model-data integration</p> <p>Domain: Remote Sensing, Dynamic Vegetation Modelling</p> <p>Data: multivariate climate and remote sensing data, large, gridded data</p> <p>Outcomes: A case study to demonstrate a model data integration framework that incorporates observational data into dynamic global vegetation models to optimize model outcomes.</p> <p>https://github.com/fanfan987/NFDI_MDI.git</p> <p>Roadmap: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8033473</p>
Statistical Learning	<p>Long title: Statistical learning to assess the factors underlying environmental changes</p> <p>Domain: Remote Sensing, Earth System Data Science</p> <p>Data: multivariate climate and remote sensing data, large, gridded data, data cubes</p> <p>Outcomes: The Julia package YAXArraysToolbox containing basic operations to efficiently process and visualize large gridded data and tools to perform data-driven attribution.</p> <p>https://github.com/dpabon/YAXArraysToolbox.jl</p> <p>Jupyter Notebooks demonstrating the functionality of the newly developed package.</p> <p>https://github.com/dpabon/YAXArraysToolboxNotebooks/tree/v0.0.2</p> <p>Roadmap: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7995187</p>
WSF	<p>Long title: World Settlement Footprint (WSF)</p> <p>Domain: Remote Sensing</p> <p>Data: global gridded data set on human settlements</p> <p>Outcomes: Standardized provision of several datasets of the WFS suite and IÖR monitor data as a STAC catalog that enables optimized cloud based retrieval and analysis.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.15489/twg5xsnquw84</p> <p>Roadmap: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7897531</p>

4 Synthesis results

As described above we have gathered information from the pilot roadmaps compiled in five categories, namely 1) FAIRness and Openness (with further sub-categories) 2) Tools and Software 3) Outreach and education 4) Collaborations and community networks and 5) Further challenges and outlook. For each of those categories we will describe best practices as well as challenges and issues faced by the pilots. There are certain overlaps of the categories and some aspects are interconnected.

4.1 FAIRness and Openness

Aspects of Open Science are partly reflected in the FAIR principles and vice versa. We decided to focus on implementation aspects that relate to specific technologies instead of choosing the aspects of FAIR as categories. Thus the three chosen sub-categories contain varying aspects of both concepts.

4.1.1 Open-source, open data and free access

This section focuses mainly on findability, accessibility and reusability.

The term **open-source** refers to the open accessibility of software. All pilots that produced software have already provided their code as open-source or have committed in their roadmap to do so in the future. Also they relied on other open-source software in the development of their own code, e.g., GRASS GIS and QGIS (GeoFRESH, WSF). The already open-sourced code was published in a GitHub repository with a respective license for reuse (PAMbase, ESMValTool, GeoFRESH, Statistical Learning, Complex Semantics). Licenses that deliberately allow reuse are very common, however one pilot encountered limitations for code integration due to licensing, which will be further elaborated in the license section (ESMValTool).

With regards to the **open and free access to data**, all pilots that provide data with their tool secure cost-free access (WSF, PAMbase, GeoFRESH, Marine Seismic Data). For some pilots' data - depending on the platform or project origin - users possibly need to register for a free user account to access the data (PAMbase, Marine Seismic Data). For marine seismic data newly acquired data will be made available freely after a moratorium period (two-year plus two-year) to "ensure the acceptability of the concept in the community" (Marine Seismic Data).

This comment on the acceptability of data sharing points us to the fact that data sharing is not yet common in all ESS sub-disciplines and we need both technical facilities but also tackle the individual and community-wide willingness to share research data for reuse.

Platforms developed within the scope of a pilot or used for data publication are openly accessible, some require registration for extended functionalities or data download (Lexcube, Marine Seismic, GeoFRESH, PAMbase).

With regard to the design of a platform or service and using a broader definition of accessibility, some services provide standardized APIs for data access (WSF) and different viewers and plugins that lower entry barriers for users with less/no programming skills (GeoFRESH, PAMbase, WSF, Marine Seismic data). Also the focus on cloud based solutions could help to make certain data and analysis tools more accessible across institutions and provide a more equitable access for many researchers, not only the ones based at institutions with large capacities for HPC and data storage (ESMValTool, WSF, Statistical Learning).

Concepts, guidelines or **metadata schemes** developed in pilot projects have been made freely and publicly available (Interop and Reuse, Complex Semantics).

As expected by NFDI4Earth pilot projects, they are committed to FAIR and open software, data and platforms and develop their solutions accordingly. Our analysis revealed that the willingness to share data timely after acquisition differs across communities. We assume this is also related to the type of data and the individual efforts and resources involved in the data acquisition e.g., marine seismic data from individual research cruises or lab analysis vs. remote sensing data. Apart from developing technical solutions, pilots also trigger discussions and shape community processes on the FAIRness and Openness of the research practices in their communities.

4.1.2 Licenses and persistent identifiers

This section focuses mainly on the findability and reusability aspects of the FAIR principles.

As mentioned above, **open-source code** by pilots was published with a corresponding license e.g., Apache, GNU General Public License, MIT license (PAMbase, ESMValTool, GeoFRESH, Statistical Learning, Complex Semantics). It is beyond of the scope of this report to explain the different licenses and their individual advantages in detail, however we find it worth mentioning that one pilot reported difficulties in code integration due to licensing of code. ESMValTool is licensed with Apache 2.0 whereas the existing machine learning algorithm they wanted to integrate into ESMValTool was licensed under GPL 3. It is a known issue that GPL 3 software cannot be seamlessly integrated into Apache 2.0 code². The pilot researchers thus had to build a workaround for the integration.

Regarding published **data** WSF used a Creative Commons license, PAMbase encourages their users to assign a license of their choice when uploading sound recordings to their platform. For

² <https://www.apache.org/licenses/GPL-compatibility.html>

Marine Seismic data in the report no specific licenses were mentioned, only that data will be “freely available”. Especially in communities where the willingness to share data is still lower, licensing could be an incentive to publish data by assuring only the desired reuse of the data for data providers.

Unique and persistent identifiers are/will be assigned to published datasets (WSF, GeoFRESH, Complex Semantics, Marine Seismic Data) and for better findability of datasets, users are encouraged to provide DOIs of data-related publications and ORCID IDs of the data creators (PAMbase).

The usage of licenses is widely adopted among pilot projects. It is also supported by a user-friendly integration making it easy to assign licenses as in GitHub or on self-developed platforms (PAMbase). We recommend choosing licenses as open and liberal as possible and being aware of possible incompatibilities.

The use of persistent identifiers for datasets, publications and involved persons is explicitly encouraged and common practice among pilots. Roadmaps and accompanying files of all pilots were published on Zenodo with a DOI and CC license.

4.1.3 Metadata and standards

This section focuses mainly on the interoperability aspect of the FAIR principles.

For four pilots one of their project goals was to **develop new metadata standards** for data of their domain (Complex Semantics, Marine Seismic Data, PAMbase, Interop and Reuse). Apart from creating standards for newly acquired data this also includes the application of those standards to legacy data and development of conversion pipelines (Complex Semantics, Marine Seismic Data). A pilot reported the challenge to balance and negotiate between exhaustive, very specific standards and more general ones that are more easily adapted (Marine Seismic Data). For the Complex Semantics pilot also different “schools” of taxonomic identification and how to unify them had to be considered. This also includes community work for which we have a dedicated section below. This very pilot also made use of an existing standardized ontology (WoRMS) to resolve semantic/taxonomic ambiguities. The Interop and Reuse pilot - who strived to represent the whole laboratory workflow in a metadata scheme from instruments and data acquisition to data processing and analysis - could also rely on existing standards or systems, e.g. the UCUM system that enables a translation and unambiguous representation of units across disciplines. The aim of this pilot was to develop a flexible metadata database model that should be expandable to other disciplines using their discipline-specific thesauri. This is still on a conceptual level though, as there is no technical implementation of the developed model yet.

Other pilots, especially from remote sensing and modeling communities, could rely on well **established standards**, like the CMOR/CF standard for climate data (ESMValTool) and

common data formats for gridded data like netCDF and zarr that reflect those standards and have dedicated software tools/packages (ESMValTool, WSF, Lexcube, Statistical Learning, Seamless Integration). We see an increased attention to cloud optimized formats that support functionalities for faster and more efficient computations like lazy loading (ESMValTool, WSF, Lexcube, Statistical Learning). However not all software tools have adapted the same formats, which required workarounds or also loss of those functionalities (ESMValTool). Here we also see that technological change - for example changing the core format used in a community developed software - does not only rely on the technical implementation but on a community consensus to do so in the first place.

We see that ESS communities that rely on long tail data derived from potentially less standardized because more scattered and less frequent data acquisition and lab analysis procedures (e.g. Complex Semantics, Marine Seismic Data, Interop and Reuse) face different and possibly more severe challenges in standardization and alignment than communities like modeling and remote sensing, where data is per se very evenly structured in its format and stem from less and more centralized sources (like ESA).

4.2 Tools and software

Five pilots relied on the **Python** programming language in (Lexcube, PAMbase, WSF, ESMValTool, Marine Seismic Data), three used R (GeoFRESH, Complex Semantics, Seamless Integration), one developed a package in Julia (Statistical Learning) reflecting the most commonly used scientific programming languages in ESS that are open-source and have a big or growing user community.

Three pilots have used or plan to use **Jupyter Notebooks** for interactive demonstration or for easy and transparent execution of processing pipelines (WSF, Marine Seismic Data, Statistical Learning).

Furthermore QGIS was used as open-source GIS software (WSF, GeoFRESH), and for **web development** tools like R-Shiny (GeoFRESH) and PHP/JavaScript/CSS/HTML (PAMbase). For **database** implementations pilots chose MySQL (PAMbase) and PostgreSQL/PostGIS (GeoFRESH). Only one pilot containerized their software into a **docker container** for higher reproducibility (PAMbase).

4.3 Outreach and education

The majority of the pilots have or plan to present their outcomes and ideas at scientific **conferences and workshops** according to their roadmaps. Two pilots used the social media twitter to create visibility for their tools (Lexcube, ESMValTool). Scientific publications have

been published and are planned by several pilots (GeoFRESH, PAMBase, Complex Semantics, Lexcube, Interop and Reuse).

Five pilots developed a dedicated online documentation, tutorials or jupyter notebooks to explain the usage and demonstrate the functionalities of their tools (GeoFRESH, WSF, ESMValTool, Lexcube, Statistical Learning).

4.4 Collaborations and community networks

As seen in the previous sections the technological implementation of research data management workflows are accompanied by **community processes** that are decisive for the uptake and development of certain practices and solutions. Different communities of the ESS show varying degrees of established standards and existing collaborations. The **connectedness of a community** influences how easy it is to discuss and implement community standards and solutions.

For some of the pilots it was an inherent goal to connect communities or domains and enable interdisciplinary analysis (PAMbase, GeoFRESH). PAMbase experienced that the passive acoustic monitoring (PAM) community in Germany has not yet a strong network. They found it hard to reach the stakeholders. In a survey on needs and experiences with PAM data they only got little feedback and were lacking diverse communication channels, mailing lists or alike to further spread the survey.

The connectedness of a community has a historical component and is also dependent on individuals active in the research field. Further influences are the size of the community, the age of the research branch or technology and established ways of communication and exchange like mailing lists, regular conferences or workshops. As previously mentioned also the type of data generated and the involved acquisition processes might influence the community process.

For example for Marine Seismic Data the community is rather small and only spread across a handful of institutions in Germany. Here the exchange with international players also plays a crucial role. A smaller community makes it easier to reach all involved persons but progress might also be more dependent on the convictions and openness to change of individuals.

4.5 Further challenges and outlook

A further constraint pilots experienced in the course of their project phase was the limited time of one year, especially if implementations or processes were more time consuming than initially envisioned (Lexcube, ESMValTool, Marine Seismic Data). For ESMValTool the further development of their software depended on developments and decisions in other communities.

Marine Seismic Data reported the missing funds to proceed with data rescue of a vast amount of non-digitized data. In Interop and Reuse they lacked the IT infrastructure and a skilled person to perform the planned technical implementation of their metadata database model.

With regards to the continuation of the developments started in the pilot projects, to the knowledge of the author, eight projects have secured other funding to continue (parts of) their work (Lexcube, WSF, GeoFRESH, MarineSeismic, Complex Semantics, ESMValTool, Statistical Learning). Two projects have submitted a follow up proposal for the second call for pilots (GeoFRESH, PAMbase) and GeoFRESH got accepted for funding.

5 Lessons learned in the pilot coordination

Besides providing a useful RDM tool for their ESS subdomain, pilots were envisioned to collaborate and be integrated into different measures of the NFDI4Earth consortium. As pilot coordination, we have gathered some lessons learned on this during the first cohort of pilots. For further information please also refer to the annual report of the pilot coordination (Deliverable D1.1.1 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7895675>).

We noted that the **identification with the consortium** and motivation for collaborations varied significantly among the pilot projects. Many pilots explicitly saw their project in the overarching efforts and context of NFDI4Earth, whereas others were more focused on the individual scope of their project. To address this we plan to provide even more dedicated information for future pilots and organize meetings that allow for more time and fewer participants.

The initial concept of **clustering and merging pilot projects** faced certain limitations during implementation. Due to funding reduction, the number of rounds and pilots per round are fewer than initially planned. Furthermore, the diverse selection of domains and goals within the pilot projects presented challenges in collaborating across domains. As mentioned, we did receive follow-up applications in the second pilot call, they however merged with other institutions from the same field instead of fellow pilots.

With respect to the **technical integration** into the consortium, the NFDI4Earth products, such as OneStop4All, Living Handbook, and Knowledge Hub, were not sufficiently developed by the end of the first pilot cohort. Thus, pilot outcomes could not be directly included in these tools. However, information on the pilot outcomes has been made available to the consortium and the general public via project reports on Zenodo, the NFDI4Earth website and talks and posters at the NFDI4Earth Plenary (Dresden, May 31st - June 2nd, 2023). Furthermore, we initiated relevant discussions and preparations with colleagues from other measures to facilitate future integration.

To enhance integration into the consortium and foster identification with the overarching goals, we suggest to establish a **mid-term evaluation board** for the next pilot round comprising members from different project measures. This board would play a pivotal role in ensuring better integration, value, and usefulness of the pilot projects for the community. Additionally, considering the creation of a Special Issue dedicated to showcasing the outcomes and achievements of the pilot projects can significantly increase their visibility.

6 Conclusions

As embedded in the name pilot, the different projects piloted ideas and the results range from ready-to-use implementations, prototypes to the development and proof of concepts and standards. The results have reached different levels of maturity and completeness due to various constraints laid out in previous sections. Pilots have triggered discussions and processes in communities on standard developments, alignment and harmonization of procedures, data publication and sharing.

Pilots have shown the successful adaptation of FAIR and Open Science principles but also revealed existing challenges. We have seen that changes in RDM practices do not only rely on the availability of technological solutions but on the capacities and structure of a community to reach consensus, align practices and foster collaborations across institutions.

It is great to see that the majority of pilot developments continue and NFDI4Earth should ensure and encourage further collaborations and exchange beyond the pilot funding period. The pilot coordination office, author of this report, acts as a connecting node here. As seen during the first pilot phase it is important to raise identification with the overarching aims of the consortium, create visibility for the pilot outcomes within and outside of NFDI4Earth and integrate colleagues from other NFDI4Earth measures early on.

The pilots provide valuable insights into subdomains of the ESS for NFDI4Earth and their specific challenges that have to be considered in the major endeavor of the consortium.